

to NO₂ groups⁴ appeared at 1 570–1 580 and 1 400 cm⁻¹, when the thiadiazoles were substituted.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer.

5-Arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles⁵ (1): A mixture of 4-arylthiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol), CS₂ (0.01 mol) and DMF (15 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~1.5 h. The excess of solvent was then removed by distillation. On cooling and keeping the solution for sometime, the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish the desired compound (68%).

Polynitroarylthio derivative of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2): To 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.005 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol by warming, was added a warm solution of 10% NaOH (2 ml) and then refluxed for ~30 min. The resulting light green solution was filtered. To the filtrate was slowly added a solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.5 mol) in alcohol and the mixture shaken, when yellow coloured compounds separated instantaneously. The flask was then kept in warm water to ensure the completion of the reaction and kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol.

Results and Discussion

The 2-polynitroarylthio derivatives of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles are insoluble in water, but dissolve in acetone, chloroform and hot acetic acid. Their melting point and yields are recorded in Table 1.

The thiadiazole derivatives were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Phoma exigua* using Czapek Dox nutrient medium. All the tested compounds possessed significant antifungal activities at 1:10000 concentration. The most active compound of the series was sl. no. 11 (Table 1) which inhibited the growth of all the three fungi significantly; it inhibited the growth of *Aspergillus niger* to the extent of 89.3%. In general, the presence of chlorine atom in R² at C₅ decreased fungitoxicity. Replacement of 4-OCH₃ group by 4-OC₂H₅ has been found to increase fungitoxicity. The increase in the number of nitro groups in R² at *ortho* has been observed to increase fungitoxicity. The following is the decreasing order of fungicidal activity of thiadiazole derivatives with different R¹: benzyl > phenyl > *p*-phenetyl > *p*-anisyl > *m*-chlorophenyl > 5-chloro-*o*-tolyl > 5-nitro-*o*-tolyl.

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Interaction of Alkyl Bromides with 2,4-Dithiobiurets. Formation of Thiuret Derivatives

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It has been our experience that the alkyl groups which are saturated (such as methyl, ethyl etc.) when loaded on sulphur of the thiocarbamide, are difficult to be dislodged by breaking the S-alkyl bond. There are methods in which Raney nickel is used but it is not advisable to use it in thioureido systems¹. Thioureido compounds containing S alkyl groups can be dealkylated by using hydrogen sulphide, ammonical hydrogen sulphide or H₂S in alkaline medium^{2,3}. Verma⁴ described a method in which thiocarbamide in presence of concentrated HCl debenzylated the S-benzylisothiocarbamides.

In continuation to our work on dithiobiurets^{5,6}, we report here an interesting result observed in the reaction of 1-alkyl- or aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (1) with alkyl bromides, where alkyl group is ethyl or propyl.

On refluxing molar quantities of ethyl bromide and 1-methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (1, R=methyl) in ethanol for 1.5 h, 4-S-ethyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret (2) hydrobromide was obtained in near quantitative yields. The presence of mercaptoethyl group in 2 was evident by its reaction with alkali when ethyl-mercaptan was evolved. On continuing the reflux in ethanol for 5–6 h and working out the reaction mixture, a compound having molecular formula C₈H₈N₂S₂·HBr, m.p. 226°; ν_{max} 1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N),

was isolated, which on treatment with alkali was found to eliminate elemental sulphur. It was identified as 5-methylimino-2-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3; R=Me) hydrobromide by m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample. Similarly, refluxing 2 in ethanol also afforded 3, showing its intermediacy in the reaction. Examination of the ethanolic filtrate on glc using carbowax-400M column, showed the presence of ethyl bromide. As the formation of ethyl bromide could be possible by the reaction of ethanol with hydrobromic acid, formed during the course of reaction, methanol was substituted for ethanol, when again 3 and ethyl bromide were obtained. Thus change in the alcoholic solvent did not influence the course of reaction. Glc examination of the gaseous products showed the presence of only methanol and ethyl bromide. Phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-dithiobiurets (1; R=Ph or *p*-tolyl) similarly gave the corresponding thiurets and ethyl bromide. In the reaction of 1 with ethyl bromide in methanol in nitrogen atmosphere, only 2 could be isolated.

The proposed mechanism involves the dealkylation of the S-alkyl group of 2, affording the dithiobiuret 1, which is then readily oxidised by air to 3. This is supported by the fact that 2 remains unchanged when the reaction is carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. Change of alkyl bromide from ethyl to propyl or isopropyl, also gave 3 and the corresponding alkyl bromide, thus indicating the general nature of the reaction.

Experimental

The required 1-alkyl/aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (1) were prepared by the action of alkyl/aryl-amine on isoperthiocyanic acid⁷.

Reaction of ethyl bromide with methyl dithiobiuret (1) in ethanol: A mixture of finely powdered 1 (3 g), ethyl bromide (1.5 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 h. On cooling, dry ether was added to the reaction mixture to yield 1-methyl-4-S-ethylisodithiobiuret hydrobromide (2, R=Me; 3.2 g), m.p. 172°. On treating 2 with alkali, profuse elimination of ethyl mercaptan was observed, and with alkali plumbite solution it gave yellow precipitate of lead ethylmercaptide (Found: molecular equivalent (acidimetrically), 258.1; C, 23.15; H, 4.18; N, 16.21; S, 24.6. C₅H₁₁N₂S₂.HBr requires: mol. equiv., 258; C, 23.25; H, 4.26; N, 16.27; S, 24.8%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3200 (NH), 1595 (N=C-N), 1565, 1490, 1160 (NH-CS-NH), 1240 (S-R); pmr (Brucker 80 MW FTR spectrometer) δ (MeOH, deuterio) 1.44 (t, C-CH₃), 3.29 (q, 2 $\times$ CH₂ of CH₂CH₃ group), 3.36 (s, NH) disappears after treating with D₂O and 3.16 (s, C=NH).

A mixture of 1 (R=Me; 3 g), ethyl bromide (1.5 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and treated with dry ether and the resulting yellowish, white solid was washed with excess of acetone. The residue (1.35 g) was purified by dissolving in alcohol and reprecipitation with ether, m.p. 228°. On heating the compound with alkali, elemental sulphur was obtained (Found, C, 15.72; H, 2.58; N, 18.42; S, 27.86. C₉H₆N₂S₂Br calcd. for: C, 15.79; H, 2.63; N, 18.41; S, 28.07%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3440 (NH), 3120 (MeNH), 1590 (C=N), 1440 and 1240 cm⁻¹ (C-S). It was identified as 5-methylimino-3-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrobromide (3) through its m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample prepared by the oxidation of methyl dithiobiuret with bromine⁸.

The acetonic filtrate on treatment with ether gave very small amount of 2.

Reaction of 4-S-ethyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret hydrobromide (2) in methanol: 2 (m.p. 172°, 2 g) was refluxed in methanol (20 ml) for 6 h. On working out as described in the earlier experiment, 3 (0.8 g) was obtained. Methanolic solution from above reaction was chromatographed on glc (Tosniwal RL-04 gas chromatograph) using carbowax-400M column: column temp., 80°; detector temp., 120°, sensitivity (FID 10⁻⁸ $\times$ 1), carrier gas nitrogen flow, 60 ml/min⁻¹, retention times found: methanol, 5.2 min; ethyl bromide, 3.3 min on comparison with authentic samples.

Reaction of ethyl/phenyl/p-tolyldithiobiurets (1, R=Et, Ph, p-tolyl) with ethyl bromide in methanol: The reaction of 1 (R=Ph, p-tolyl and ethyl) with molar quantities of ethyl bromide under similar reaction conditions afforded the corresponding thiurets⁸ which were identified by m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra with authentic samples. Quantities of dithiobiurets taken and the thiurets formed are as follows: phenyl dithiobiuret (2.1 g), phenylthiuret HBr (1 g), m.p./m.m.p. 210°; p-tolyldithiobiuret (2.4 g), p-tolythiuret HBr (0.9 g), m.p./

m.m.p. 220°; ethyl dithiobiuret (3 g), ethyl thiuret HBr (1.2 g), m.p./m.m.p. 154°.

Reaction of methyl dithiobiuret (1) with propyl bromide in n-propanol. Formation of 4-S-propyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret HBr and methyl thiuret hydrobromide (3): A mixture of methyl dithiobiuret (3 g), n-propanol (20 ml) and propyl bromide (1.8 g) was refluxed for 1.5 h. 4-S-Propyl-1-methylisodithiobiuret HBr was precipitated with dry ether, when an oil was obtained which was taken up in n-propanol (20 ml), the solution refluxed for 6 h and worked up as described earlier to give 3 (R = Me; 1.1 g).

Propanolic solution from the above experiment was chromatographed on a Toshniwal RL-04 gas chromatograph using carbowax-400 M having column temp. 90°, injection port, 120° and detector, 120°, (FID)-sensitivity $10^{-8} \times 1$; the retention time for propyl bromide, 4 min; n-propanol, 11 min.

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Occurrence of (+)-Vasicinone in *Adhatoda vasica* Nees

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THE leaves of *Adhatoda vasica* Nees (Acanthaceae) are used in the indigenous system of medicine¹. The earlier workers isolated (-)-vasicinone and (±)-vasicinone from the leaves of *A. vasica*

Nees^{2,3}. We now report for the first time the occurrence of (+)-vasicinone in the leaves of *A. vasica*.

The concentrated MeOH extract of defatted leaves of *A. vasica* (a voucher specimen is preserved in our laboratory) was churned with 5% citric acid and filtered. The filtrate was shaken with CHCl_3 and removed the non-alkaloidal matter and then made alkaline with cold ammonia to pH 9 and extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 solution was extracted with 1% HCl. The acidic solution was made alkaline with cold ammonia (pH 9) and extracted with chloroform. On concentration, the chloroform solution yielded (±)-vasicine, m.p. 198–99°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0^{\circ}$ ^{3,4}. The mother liquor upon column chromatography over silica gel afforded another alkaloid, crystallising from chloroform–ethyl acetate, m.p. 201–02° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 148^{\circ}$ ($C=1.35 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$), showing ir spectrum similar to that reported for vasicinone⁵. Its uv, nmr and mass spectra were in concordance with those reported for (-)-vasicinone. However, the $[\alpha]_D$ of our isolated vasicinone was (+)ve and that of the authentic sample was found to be (-)ve. Further, acetylation of (+)-vasicinone with acetic anhydride–pyridine followed by chromatography over silica gel yielded the acetyl derivative, m.p. 134–35° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 10^{\circ}$ ($C=1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$) showing ir absorptions at 1755 and 1240 cm^{-1} (OCOCH_3). Thus the optical rotations of vasicinone and its corresponding acetyl derivative proved that vasicinone isolated from *A. vasica* occurs in (+) form.

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